

Anti-Nutrients- A limiting factor for use of green fodder in livestock feed

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Livestock plays an important role in Indian agriculture and rural economy. Rural population has major livelihood sources and income from livestock and poultry by selling milk, meat and egg. In India the available natural fodders are poor in quality with regards to energy, protein and minerals and vitamins, which leads to reduces production which directly affects farmers income. Although, green fodder, hay and silage contains good nutritional values, but there maintenance, ways of consumption and presence of some toxic material also alarm us. Among the different quality controlling aspects anti nutritional factors are also of prime importance. Anti-nutritional factors (ANFs) are products of secondary metabolism that are produced by normal metabolic process that interfere and affect the feed ingestion, health and production of animals. Green fodder contains these compounds called allelochemicals, which depends upon the system of cultivation (Rainfed, Irrigated or under drought condition) having deleterious or beneficial effects on livestock's.

Anti-nutritional factors

Chemical substances present in the diet which by themselves or their metabolic products arising in the system interfere with the feed utilization, reduce production or affects the health of animal.

Nitrate:

Crops like sorghum, millet, corn and sudan grass are having high levels of nitrate content and legumes can have excessive levels under certain extreme conditions like drought and harvesting immediately after rain. The above forage crops harvested for green fodder before 50 days and fed with cattle will cause nitrate poisoning. Animals fed with such grasses contains nitrates undergoes a stream of biochemical process in livestock rumen. Initially nitrate is converted into nitrite, nitrite to ammonia, ammonia to amino acids, finally to protein. Nitrite is an intermediate product and when livestock fed with high level of nitrite forages the biochemical process from nitrate to protein cannot be completed. The process will be break at nitrite production stage, it leads to the accumulation of nitrite concentration is more in the rumen. This nitrite is absorbed into blood stream directly, it converts the blood haemoglobin into methemoglobin which cannot carry oxygen molecules. Due to nitrate (nitrite poisoning) animal can dies from lack of oxygen. It is called nitrate poisoning.

Oxalate:

Soluble oxalate present in the grasses (Setaria, and cenchrus) will induce calcium deficiency in grazing animals. Certain grasses namely, guinea grass, bajra and bajra napier contain oxalate content within safe limits. If cattle fed with guinea grass and cumbu napier grass over the extended period of time it may produce toxicity. Functional activity of oxalates is, it will react with calcium affects the absorbed calcium and converted as insoluble calcium oxalate, thus by reducing calcium absorption in livestock body. Cattle and sheep are less affected because of degradation of oxalate in the rumen. Oxalate level is more in early growth stage and younger plants of cumbu napier hybrid than older plants. When the plant matures oxalate content is declined. It is advisable the livestock can be fed with CN grass after 80 to 90 days after planting (DAP). Since CN grass is a multicut, oxalate content is reduced at the increasing the interval of harvesting time. Levels of 2 per cent or more soluble oxalate can lead to acute toxicosis in ruminants. The oxalate content of grasses is highest under conditions of rapid growth with concentrations as high as 6 per cent or more of dry weight

Hydrogen cyanide:

Dry season fodders include forage sorghum, sudan grass, millet have HCN poisoning at young stage and higher its vegetative leaves than older leaves. Sorghum cultivating under

dryland or rainfed condition will have higher level of HCN than grown under irrigated condition. Water stress under dry land situation leads to increase the HCN level in vegetative leaves. Under stress condition like drought, frost and cutting and chopping can result in prussic acid poisoning. HCN is easily absorbed by blood stream and prevents oxygen absorption. Grain sorghum is high in HCN content, sudan grass has the lowest, and the sorghum-sudangrass hybrids are intermediate in HCN potential. When the animal is fed with young stage of sorghum grass, the ruminal bacteria degradation can result in HCN poisoning. Post harvesting wilting of green fodder can reduce the risk of cyanide toxicity.

Coumarin:

Gliricidia sepium is a legume tree fodders which capable of fixing atmospheric Nitrogen. It cannot be used as a fodder for many animals because of *gliricidia* toxicity. It is mainly due to the anti-nutrient called coumarin that is converted into dicoumerol by bacteria during its fermentation. Under normal feeding, leaves are used as a fodder for cattle, sheep, goats and pigs. Palatability is varies depending upon the soil and climatic condition due to presence of anti nutrient such as phenols and flavonol. It can be good forage for goats and sheep supplementation with rice, sorghum straw or other grass fodder which increasing digestibility. It can be used as energy source when mixed with maize bran and fed with goats.

Mimosin:

It is an alkaloid present in tree leguminous fodder commonly called "Subabul" (*Leucaena leucocephala*). It is a miracle tree because of its protein rich foliage (25%). It is widely grown in agro forestry systems, field bunds and also grown in non-cultivable land areas. Young and tender leaves contain mimosin which is a non-protein amino acid. To reduce toxicity effect, subabul leaves are sun/air dried. Several experiments stated that the mimosin content in the dried leaves ranges from 2.5-6%. But growing leaves and leaf tip contains upto 12%. It can be reduced with ensilaging methods. *Leucaena* leaves are soaking or washing in water will reduce their mimosin content. There is no harmful effect of the mimosin on livestock was reported when limited proportion of subabul leaves are fed with animals. More quantity of leaves fed with cattle will leads to loss of appetite, excessive salivation. However, partially dried subabul leaves fed with goats causes no deleterious effects on its health. Silage making and sun drying is the common measure to reduce the toxicity level of anti-nutrients.

Methods to remove:

HCN:

Forage grown on energy stress condition and crop not get proper irrigation, the levels of HCN is found higher in younger sorghum crop. Thus try to avoid these type of crop for feeding livestock. Post-harvest wilting and drying of Cynogenic leaves may decrease the effect of cyanide poisoning. Sorghum, Sudan and Johnson grass must be dried at least six hour before its use for feeding to livestock.

Mimosine:

Mimosine problem could be solved by genetic selection of strain of *Leucena* species containing low mimosine contents. Physical treatment like heat treatment and chemical treatment and supplementation with amino acids or with metal ions such as, and Fe, Al and Zn reduces the mimosine toxicity.

Nitrates:

Annual forages are more susceptible than perennial forage for Nitrates accumulation and toxicity. Adverse climate of drought or wet, dull weather condition are more prone to Nitrate toxicity. Following steps can reduce the risk of nitrate toxicity: Dilute the nitrate content of the total ration by feeding a combination of low and high nitrate feeds. Animal should be fed the ration, three or four times daily rather than just one meal per day. Allow cattle to sensitize with nitrate slowly to increase the nitrate content of the ration. Ensure balanced ration feeding to livestock for the level of production that is expected. Balance concentrate diet should be given along with feed contain nitrate to cattle to reduce toxicity.

Oxalate:

Rumen micro-organisms degrade dietary into formic acid and CO₂. Adaptability reduces the toxicity of oxalate in the body. Ruminants adapted to diets with high oxalate content can tolerate oxalate levels that are lethal to non-adapted animals.

Conclusion

Regional wise specific feed and fodder selection and identification of anti-nutritional as well as nutritional factor to optimize all feed resources in order to reach its goal. Various aspects of toxic principals, their effect and its remedial measure are necessary for optimal feed management and utilization of feed and forage for better animal health and production.